

NEWLY DISCOVERED TEMPLES AND SCULPTURES AT ZALOD,
DIST. PANCHAMAHALS, GUJARAT

By

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Zalod is a Taluka of Panchamahals district in Gujarat. The archaeological remains are located on the eastern bank of river Machan. They are one km away from the village Mandali Khunta and five kms. away in the east from Taluka Zalod. The site where these archaeological remains are found is known as Pancha Krishna.

These remains comprise a number of dilapidated temples and sculptures. The temples in existence at present are eleven in number (pl. I). Out of them, five have been renovated during the last fifteen years. They have been so much renovated with cement plaster and white-wash that they look modern. These temples are built of brick and stone masonry and are datable to C. 11th cen. AD. All of them consist on plan of a sanctum and a porch.

Temple No. 1

This temple is dedicated to Śiva (pl. II). In the sanctum is enshrined a *śivaliṅga* on a *yonipatta* (pl. III). It has been completely renovated and white-washed. The sanctum measures internally 1.80 mt. square. The porch resting on two pillars and two pilasters measures 2.50 × 2.60 mts. The temple has a modern conical *śikhara*.

Temple No. 2

Only the brick masonry plinth of this temple has survived (pl. IV). The superstructure has completely collapsed and the architectural members are lying strewn on the plinth. They comprise pillars, lintels and door-jambs, etc. The lintel of the sanctum-doorway is carved in the centre with seated Gaṇeśa. Of the two door-jambs of the sanctum door-way each shows on its lower part a niche containing an image of a *Śaiva-dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga*. One of them holds *triśūla* and *kapāla*, while the other holds a *triśūla* and *mātulūṅga*. One door jamb measures 1.40 × 0.40 × 0.15 mt. The other door-jamb measures 1.40 × 0.50 × 0.17 mt. The lintel of the sanctum doorway measures 1.80 × 0.40 × 0.18 mt. The stone used is bluish sandstone. The plinth of the temple measures 10.0 × 7.20 mt.

Journal of the Oriental Institute Vol. 42, Nos. 3-4, March-June, 1993 Issue, pp. 161-165.

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Temple No. 3

It has also been completely renovated. It consists on plan of a sanctum (pl. V), an *antarāla* and a porch. The sanctum doorway is carved on the lintel and door-jamb. The right flank of the sanctum-doorway shows standing Gaṅgā holding *Kalaśa* (mount crocodile shown on her left) a standing *dvārapāla* wearing a *karāṇḍamukuta* and an ascetic. The left flank shows standing Yamunā holding *kalaśa*, a standing Vaiṣṇava *dvārapāla* holding a *cakra* in his left hand and an ascetic. The lintel is carved with seated Gaṇeśa.

On a pedestal attached to the rear wall of the sanctum are installed three images of Sūrya. (pl. VI). Each of these images is carved inside a niche. Two of the images are standing in *sambhaṅga* holding lotuses in both hands, while the third image is seated cross-legged and holds lotuses in both hands. On the pedestal is carved in a niche, the charioteer Aruṇa and seven horses. The sanctum measures internally 1.25 × 1.75 mt. The *antarāla* measures 1 × 1.30 mt. The porch measures 2.10 × 2.30 mt. The sanctum has a *pañcaratha śikhara* and is *pañcaratha* in plan. This temple is dedicated to Sūrya.

Temple No. 4

It consists on plan of a sanctum, an *antarāla* and a porch (pl. VII). Its porch has completely collapsed. The *śikhara* over its sanctum has completely collapsed. The sanctum is built of brick and stone masonry. The lintel of the sanctum-doorway is carved with seated Gaṇeśa in the centre. The right flank of the doorway shows standing Gaṅgā, holding *kalaśa* in her right hand, standing Śaiva *dvārapāla* holding *triśūla* and *bijapūraka* and a standing ascetic. The left flank of the sanctum-doorway shows standing Yamunā holding a *kalaśa* in her left hand, a standing *dvārapāla* holding a *cakra* in his right hand and a standing ascetic. The left flank of the sanctum-doorway shows standing Yamunā holding a *kalaśa* in her left hand, a standing *dvārapāla* holding a *cakra* in his right hand and a standing ascetic.

Attached to the rear wall of the sanctum is a stone pedestal on which are placed five images at present (pl. VIII). The first image represents a niche containing an image of Rāma standing in *tribhaṅga* and holding arrow and bow. The second image shows a niche containing an image of two-armed Varāha in *ālīḍha* pose holding *gadā* and *śankha*. Pṛthvī is seen seated on his left elbow. The third image shows a niche containing an image of two-armed Narasimha ripping open the belly of demon Hiraṇyakaśipu. The fourth image is that of Varāha standing in *ālīḍha* pose and holding *gadā* and *śankha* in a niche. The fifth image is that of a standing two-armed female deity carrying *abhaya* and *mātulūṅga*. The sanctum internally measures 1.80 × 1.40 mt. The *antarāla* measures 1 × 1.40 mt. The porch measures 2.10 × 2.30 mt.

On the right of this temple is lying a loose door jamb carved on the lower part with three figures. The first and second figures are those of standing river goddesses and standing *dvārapālas*. The third figure shows a standing ascetic. The door-jamb measures $1.37 \times 0.37 \times 0.13$ mtrs.

Temple No. 5:

It consists on plan of a sanctum, an *antarāla* and a porch. Only the plinth of the temple has survived (pl. IX). The superstructure has completely collapsed. The following loose architectural and sculptural members of the temple are lying on the plinth (1) Three *Chhajjā* stones (2) Two door-jambes of the sanctum doorway. The first door-jamb shows a standing river goddess holding a *kalaśa* by her both hands, a standing *Vaiṣṇava dvārapāla* holding *śaṅkha* in his left hand and a standing ascetic. The second door-jamb shows a standing river goddess holding a *kalaśa* by her both hands and standing under a lotus canopy, a *Vaiṣṇava dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and holding *cakra* in his right hand and an ascetic. (3) A niche containing an image of two-armed Śiva seated in *padmāsana* and holding *triśūla* and *bijapūraka*. An architectural piece carved with two niches, of which one contains a seated image of a deity with chopped head. Buddha in *vyākhyānamudrā*, while his upper right hand holds *gadā* and his upper left hand carries a *pustaka* (5) A stone slab carved with two niches of which one contains an image of Buddha seated in *vyākhyānamudrā* while the second contains an image of four-armed Viṣṇu with his lower two hands in *vyākhyānamudrā* and the upper two holding *gadā* and *pustaka* respectively (6) A mutilated niche containing the bust of Balarāma holding *hala* in his right hand. The plinth of the temple measures 6.00×2.90 .

Temple No. 6:

The plinth of this temple measures 6.00×2.90 mt. Only the plinth of the temple has survived (pl. X). The superstructure has completely collapsed. Among the ruins lying in and around the plinth are pillars, lintels, capitals, lintel of the sanctum—doorway carved in the centre with seated Gaṇeśa and a few sculptural fragments. The torso of flying Garuḍa wearing *vaikakṣyaka* is noteworthy. (pl. XI).

Temple No. 7:

The sanctum of this temple enshrines at present two beautiful sculptures of Viṣṇu each standing in *sambhaṅga* (pl. XII), two beautiful sculptures of Viṣṇu each standing in *sambhaṅga* (a) Standing four-armed Viṣṇu with elaborate lotus halo behind the head. His upper left hand has been chopped off and he holds *varada-cum-akṣamālā cakra* and chopped off. Seated three-headed Brahmā is shown on right and seated Śiva is shown on the left of halo. Standing

cakrapuruṣa and *śaṅkhapuruṣa* are shown on the lower-part. A female devotee holding a lotus is shown on the right and a standing male attendant is shown on the left. It is a highly ornamented image. (b) Four-armed Viṣṇu standing in *samabhaṅga*. His lower two hands have been completely chopped off. His upper two hands hold *cakra* and *śaṅkha*. *Śaṅkha* and *Cakrapuruṣas* are shown standing. A female and a male devotee are shown standing. Brahmā is shown seated on right and Śiva is shown on the left seated on the head of Viṣṇu. The porch of the temple is completely collapsed. The sanctum and *antarāla* are modern (pl. XIII). The plinth measures 9.60 × 4.20 mts.

Temple No. 8:

A completely renovated temple. It enshrines an image of a Hunuman and is in worship (pl. XIV). It consists only of a sanctum measuring 2.65 × 1.90 mt.

Temple No. 9:

It consists of plan of a sanctum, an *antarāla* and a porch. It measures externally 6.40 × 3.20 mt. The sanctum-doorway is carved on either side with figures of standing river-goddess, standing *Śaiva dvārapāla* and an ascetic. The doorway lintel is carved with seated Gaṇeśa in the centre. The pedestal attached to the rear wall of the sanctum enshrines two images (i) standing Śiva Pārvatī (pl. XV). Both of the right hands of Śiva have been chopped off. His right hand carries *sarpa*. Pārvatī carries a *liṅga* and a mirror. Nandī is shown standing behind standing Gaṇeśa shown on the left. It is a highly ornamented image each in a niche, one above the other. They are from bottom upwards Balarāma holding a *musala* in his left hand, Paraśurāma and Narasiṃha.

Temple No. 10:

Only the plinth of the sanctum of temple No. 10 has survived which measures 3.10 × 2.70 mts. In the sanctum is kept a loose fragment of the upper portion of the *parikara* of *daśāvatāra* Viṣṇu carved with three niches which contain respectively Viṣṇu in *vyākhyānamūdra* and Kalki riding a horse (pl. XVI).

Temple No. 11:

It consists on plan of a sanctum an *antarāla* and a porch (pl. XVII). It measures externally 6.00 × 2.80 mts. The sanctum enshrines Gaṇeśa (1) Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitāsana* carrying dagger, *paraśu*, *padma* and chopped *modakapātra* (2) Two-armed Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *padma* and *modakapātra*. It is a brick temple and has been completely renovated.

Hero stone kept in compound:

There is a Hero stone kept in the Compound of the temples. It measures 1.40 × .29 × .29 mts. It bears an inscription in Devanāgarī dated VS 1366. Carved on the top on four faces of the slab are shown (i) a warrior holding

Plate: I
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat) General View of temples
from West

Plate: II
Zalod Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple, No. 1 General view from South

Plate : III
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 1 The Sivalinga inside the Sanctum

Plate : IV
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 2 General View showing the ruins of the temple

Plate : V
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 3 General View from North

Plate : VI
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat State)
Temple No. 3 Images of Surya in the Sanctum

Plate : VII

Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 4 General View from south-east

Plate : VIII

Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 4 Images of Rasna, Varaha and Nrisimha kept in the
Sanctum

Plate : IX
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 5 General view showing door Jamhs

Plate : X
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 6 General view showing ruins

Plate : XI
Zalod, Distt Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No 7 Torro of Garuda

Plate : XIII
Zalod, Distt Panchamahals Gujarat)
Temple No. 7 General View

Plate : XIV
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 8 Image of Hanuman inside the sanctum

Plate : XVI
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 10 General view showing ruins

Plate : XVII
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Temple No. 11

Plate : XIX
Zalod, Distt. Panchamahals (Gujarat)
Hero stone kept in the compound

- sword and a shield and going to battle field. (ii) Sun and moon symbols
(iii) Warrior worshipping with folded hands, two *śivaliṅgas* in the shrine.
(iv) Warrior with chopped head standing in *añjalimudrā* (pl. XIX).

This group of temples is picturesquely situated on a mound on the river bank.

The aforesaid temples and sculptures from Zalod are beautiful specimens of the temple art and architecture of Panchamahals district. They belong to Śaiva, Vaiṣṇava and Saura pantheons and are assignable to eleventh century A.D. They were built during the reign of the Solanki dynasty of Gujarat. They constitute important landmarks of Solanki temple architecture and protection by the Government of Gujarat. At present, they are looked after by the villagers and are in living worship.

Reference:

1. Krishna Deva, *Temples of North India*, New Delhi, 1969. pp. 45-48.